

كلية الدراسات المصرفية والمالية
College of Banking and Financial Studies

ICBFB - 2019

International Conference on
Banking, Finance and Business

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

April 24 – 25, 2019
CBFS, Muscat,
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CUSTOMERS AWARENESS AND PERCEPTIONS TOWARDS GREEN BANKING.

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ABSTRACT

In the modern of banking context, sustainable development is achieved through concept of banking in general and green banking in particular. Green banking is a eco-friendly banking practice that encourages their customers to reduce the carbon foot print through their environmental friendly banking practices. This paper is an attempt to study the customer's awareness and perceptions towards green banking in Bhatkal Taluk's nationalised banks. The data is collected from the customers through primary as well as secondary data method. The study concludes that the customers of the banks are aware of the Green banking services.

Keywords: Awareness, Online Banking, Nationalized banks, Customers, Rural